

LEVERAGING GENERATIVE ADVERSARIAL NETWORKS IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT FOR TASK ESTIMATION

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Abstract: *Accurate project estimation remains one of the most challenging aspects of project management, particularly when historical data is scarce, or project complexity is high. This study explores the use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to generate synthetic project data, including task duration estimates, by learning from historical data. Jira migration projects were used as an example. A new project with a distinct scope was introduced, and four GAN model variations were evaluated using Mean Absolute Error and Fréchet Distance to identify the most effective combination of parameters. The selected model was then used to generate task estimates for the new project, which were compared against traditional estimates based on the average values. Results show that the GAN-generated estimates were more conservative, highlighting potential hidden complexities and offering improved risk buffering. This approach demonstrates the potential of AI to enhance forecasting accuracy in project management and lays the foundation for future work on synthetic estimation of resources allocation, dependencies modeling, and risks identification.*

Keywords: *project management, generative adversarial networks, synthetic data.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last 10 years, soft computing techniques are massively applied and used in transforming various business domains. In the project management area, soft computing techniques, especially neural networks are used to allow more accurate forecasting of project outcomes. The benefits could be seen in identifying potential delays, cost overruns, and resource constraints before they occur, allowing for proactive adjustments.

AI technologies, including machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics, are transforming project management by enabling more accurate forecasting of project outcomes. These tools assist in identifying potential delays, cost overruns, and resource constraints before they occur, allowing for proactive adjustments. For instance, AI-driven models have been utilized to predict project performance metrics in urban infrastructure projects, enhancing the ability to manage timelines and budgets effectively (Sadeghi, 2024). Additionally, AI facilitates the automation of routine tasks, improves stakeholder communication through natural language processing, and supports decision-making processes by analyzing large datasets for actionable insights (Al-Arafat et al., 2024; Lan, 2023). The integration of AI into project management practices leads to increased efficiency, reduced human error, and more informed strategic planning (Davahli, 2020).

This paper deals with a specific area of the application of AI techniques in project estimations and predictive analytics, and more specifically with the data scarcity challenge. Accurate project estimations rely heavily on the availability of high-quality historical data, which can be limited in certain domains. AI techniques, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), offer a way to generate realistic synthetic data to overcome this limitation, enabling more accurate decision-making and risk assessment in project management. Various synthetic data generation techniques, including GANs, VAEs, and data augmentation methods, have been explored for project management applications. These techniques have been used for cross-project fault prediction (Wang et al., 2025), predictive process monitoring (Lin, Khan, & Latif, 2025), and risk identification in supply chains (Hu et al., 2025). These approaches allow project managers to generate realistic project scenarios, simulate potential risks, and optimize resource allocation when historical data is scarce or incomplete, making them valuable tools for project planning and decision-making.

The focus of this paper is on applying GANs for generating project task estimates, based on the resource allocations, dependencies, timelines, and other constraints, for a new project with a certain level of complexity. This approach uses examples from similar past projects to train the GAN model, allowing it to produce realistic project data. The obtained results are then compared with traditional estimation approaches to assess accuracy, variance, and overall project planning efficiency.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a short overview of GANs and their application in project management. Section 3 describes the experiment design, including steps and specific considerations for applying GANs to project estimation. Section 4 presents the results of the experiment, followed by a summary of findings, concluding remarks, and proposals for future work in Section 5.

2. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF GENERATIVE ADVERSARIAL NETWORKS

Generative Adversarial Networks consist of two neural networks (a Generator and a Discriminator) competing in a zero-sum game (Goodfellow et al., 2014). GANs could learn to generate realistic data without labeled training examples. So far, this approach has been applied to image synthesis, text generation, data augmentation, and now even project task simulation. GANs are a class of machine learning frameworks designed to generate realistic synthetic data. They work by training two neural networks in tandem—Generator that creates synthetic data trying to mimic the real data, and Discriminator, with the role to evaluate the quality of the generated data by distinguishing it from real data. The two networks are set up as adversaries in a zero-sum game. The Generator tries to "fool" the Discriminator by producing data as realistic as possible. The Discriminator attempts to correctly classify data as either real (from the actual data distribution) or fake (produced by the Generator).

This approach with two networks has found diverse applications across various business domains, including project management. One study explores the application of GANs to enhance credit risk identification in supply chains (Hu et al., 2025). In another paper authors Lin, Khan and Latif (2025) proposes a novel adversarial training framework for next event prediction in business processes, and highlights the importance of using Generative Adversarial Nets in Predictive Business Process Monitoring domain. Also, in the (Wang et al., 2025), authors considered using GANs for defect prediction across different software projects.

GANs work following next steps:

1. Initialize the Networks: Both the Generator and Discriminator are initialized with random weights.
2. Training Loop: (a) The Generator creates synthetic data; (b) The Discriminator evaluates the generated data; (c) Feedback from the Discriminator is used to update both networks.
3. Convergence: The process continues until the Generator becomes good enough that the Discriminator cannot distinguish real from synthetic data.

The results generated by the GANs aim to replicate realistic patterns and relationships found in historical data. In the context of project management, these networks are enabling the generation of plausible task breakdowns and resource plans for any new or hypothetical projects. The GANs learn to simulate complex dependencies and estimation behaviors that are otherwise difficult to recognize and model manually. The output can support project managers in scenarios such as planning, rough forecasting, and improving estimation accuracy when limited data is available.

3. EXPERIMENT OVERVIEW

3.1 Purpose and goal of the experiment

The purpose of this experiment is to evaluate if GANs can be effectively used for estimating project tasks, resource utilization, and dependencies in complex migration projects. This includes comparing synthetically generated data with traditional estimation approaches to assess accuracy, variance, and overall project planning efficiency. Specifically, it aims to determine if GANs can provide more accurate and realistic task duration estimates, resource allocations, and timelines for complex Jira migration projects.

Five project examples related to the migration of the project management tools are used for this purpose:

- Project 1: Simple Jira Core Migration (On Time)
 - Basic Jira Core migration without Confluence or plugins.
 - 6 tasks, including data backup, migration, and closure.
- Project 2: Jira and Confluence Migration (Delayed)
 - More complex migration involving multiple systems and plugins.
 - 7 tasks, including plugin compatibility testing and user training.

- Project 3: Comprehensive Migration with Jira Service Management (On Time)
 - Includes Jira, Confluence, and JSM with automation rules.
 - 8 tasks, including custom workflow migration and automation.
- Project 4: Complex Migration with Custom Plugins (Delayed)
 - High-security migration with custom plugins and third-party integrations.
 - 8 tasks, including security review and plugin compatibility testing.
- Project 5: Multi-Instance Consolidation (On Time)
 - Consolidates multiple Jira and Confluence instances.
 - 8 tasks, including instance analysis, consolidation, and scripting.

The projects are described using following attributes: (a) Task duration: Estimated and Actual logged times; (b) Resource Assignments: Specific team members for each task; (c) Resource Utilization: Utilization percentages based on logged time; (d) Milestones and Dependencies: Key project milestones and critical task sequences; (e) Cost Breakdown: Licensing, labor, training, and contingency costs.

New project for which data will need to be generated represents a complex Jira migration project, and includes more complex requirements, as well as slightly different scope, as provided below: (a) Migrate Jira Software from Instance A to Instance B; (b) Migrate automation rules from Instance A to Instance B; (c) Establish a new SYNC plugin connection between Instance B and Instance C; (d) Migrate specific users to Instance B; (e) Perform two migration rehearsals; (f) Conduct user training for Instance B.

This project is more complex than the previous five examples that are available, as it involves not just the migration of data but also the transfer of complex automation rules, user accounts, and plugin configurations. Additionally, the SYNC connection setup between two separate instances introduces unique technical challenges that require careful planning and execution. The need for multiple rehearsals and user training further adds to the project's complexity, making it an ideal candidate for evaluating the effectiveness of GAN-based estimation.

3.2 Experiment stages

The experiment was conducted following next steps.

Data Preparation for GANs: Key features were extracted from five existing migration projects to serve as input for the GAN models. The data underwent cleaning, structuring, and normalization to ensure consistency and quality for training. Important elements such as task durations, resource utilization, and task dependencies were included in the prepared dataset.

GAN Models Training: Four different GAN models were used to generate realistic project task data. These models were trained using the cleaned and structured data.

Models Evaluation and Accuracy: The performance of the GAN models was assessed using MAE as well as the Wasserstein distance to measure the similarity between generated and real data distributions.

Synthetic Data Generation: Using the trained GAN models, synthetic task estimates were generated for a new migration project (Project 6). The generated data included predicted task durations, required resources, and task dependencies to simulate a realistic project plan.

Traditional Estimation (Baseline): For comparison, traditional estimation methods were applied to Project 6 using historical data. Estimates for task durations, resource allocation, and project timelines were created to serve as a baseline dataset.

Evaluation and Comparison: Finally, the GAN-generated data were evaluated against the traditional estimates. The comparison focused on accuracy, variance in predictions, and the overall efficiency of the projected timelines, providing insights into the potential benefits of GAN-based estimation methods.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Models training performances

For this experiment, 4 different variances of GANs were used, as provided in Table 1. The four model variants (V1–V4) are designed and proposed by the domain expert to explore the impact of training duration, batch size, regularization techniques, and loss functions on GAN performance for project estimation tasks. Training results are provided in Figures 1-4.

Table 1: Models variations included in the experiment

Variant	Epochs	Batch Size	Architecture	Loss
V1	1000	32	Default (Linear + ReLU)	Binary Cross Entropy (BCE)
V2	2000	64	Same as V1	BCE
V3	1500	32	With BatchNorm + Dropout	BCE
V4	1000	32	Same as V1	Wasserstein (WGAN)

Figure 1: GAN V1, 1000 Epochs, 32 batch size

Figure 2: GAN V2, 2000 Epochs, 64 batch size

Figure 3: GAN V3, 1500 Epochs, 32 batch size

Figure 4: GAN V4, 1000 Epochs, 32 batch size

Different performance levels were observed in terms on how well GANs could learn and generate realistic project data. Model V1 showed a healthy balance between learning and accuracy, steadily improving and generating reliable results. Model V2, trained longer with more data per batch, was the most stable and showed the best overall learning behavior. Model V3, which added techniques to prevent overfitting, unfortunately ended up with one part of the system becoming too dominant, leading to weaker results. Model V4 showed very limited progress and didn't learn useful patterns effectively. All this indicates that V2 is the most stable, followed by V1. In case of the remaining two models, V3 and V4, both showed some signs of inefficiency.

Next, performance metrics were calculated and presented in Table 2. We are generating project estimations like durations, resource utilization, etc., thus MAE is the first choice. It tells how far off are synthetic estimations from historical ones, and it's easy to interpret. On the other hand, Fréchet Distance measures the difference in distribution between the real and generated data, considering both central tendency and relationships between features. GANs may generate values that look accurate individually but don't follow the same patterns as the original data. Thus, Fréchet Distance seems to be a good choice since it catches those deeper mismatches in structure. This combination of pointwise and distributional metrics is a common and recommended approach in evaluating generative model performance (Sajjadi et al., 2018).

Model V3 showed the best performance, i.e. it generates synthetic project data that is not only more accurate (lower MAE) but also more structurally realistic (lower Fréchet Distance). V1 and V2 perform almost identically despite different training setups, indicating that simply increasing epochs or batch size does not improve performance. Finally, model V4 shows potential but didn't outperform BCE-based models in this setup.

Table 2: Models performance metrics

Variant	MAE	Fréchet Distance
V1	0.491856	2.630361
V2	0.491856	2.630382
V3	0.30594	0.457385
V4	0.488585	2.598531

4.2. Synthetic data generation and comparison with the traditional estimation

In this step, synthetic data for a new project scenario is generated using the best-performing GAN model V3. The generator, trained on the original dataset, is used to replicate the underlying distribution of task estimations and workload patterns. This synthetic dataset is intended to support further experimentation and evaluation, particularly in contexts where real project data is limited or unavailable. Synthetic data is provided in the Table 3, column 2. Total Duration of the new project is 149.52 days. In addition, comparing to the historically available data regarding the tasks that were executed in the previous 5 projects, there are three tasks that are new, and historical data about their durations are not available. Those three tasks are highlighted in the table and are: Identify and Document Ticket Content Rules, Migrate Users to Instance B and Establish SYNC Connection between Instance B and Instance C. In the next section, to compare the total duration, arbitrary value for those new tasks will be used.

Table 3: Synthetic data – Task estimates for Project 6

Task	Estimates (Synthetic)	New task	Estimates (Traditional)
Project Kickoff	12.62	No	3.2
Identify and Document Ticket Content Rules	13.6	Yes	8.8
Export Automation Rules from Instance A	14.42	No	6
Setup New Instance B	12.35	No	15
Migrate Users to Instance B	18.24	Yes	8.8
Establish SYNC Connection between Instance B and Instance C	11.58	Yes	8.8
Migrate Automation Rules to Instance B	5.67	No	6
Migration Rehearsal 1	2.71	No	14
Backup Instance A	5.79	No	7.66
Migration Rehearsal 2	7.14	No	14
Final Data Migration	11.95	No	14
Post-Migration Validation	11.07	No	6.25
Staff Training for New Instance B	15.97	No	7.2
Project Closure	6.41	No	3.6
Total Duration in days	149.52		123.31

Furthermore, the comparison of model V3 estimations with the traditional approach where average values are calculated for the tasks based on the historically available data (Table 3, column 4) is provided. These values are used as a baseline, and the complete comparison is provided in the next table. As noted in the previous chapter, there are three new tasks for which historical data doesn't exist. For the comparison of the total duration of the new project between the average and values that were synthetically generated, for each new task, the average duration of all other tasks was used (8.8 days).

The synthetic estimates, generated using a GAN-based approach with model V3, result in a total of 149.52 days for the new project, whereas the traditional estimation approach totals 123.31 days. This represents a 21% increase and suggests that the synthetic model included more conservative durations, potentially accounting for hidden complexities. Notably, some tasks such as "Migrate Users to Instance B," "Project Kickoff," and "Staff Training" are significantly higher in the synthetic model, highlighting areas where traditional estimation may underestimate effort. Overall, the synthetic estimates offer a broader buffer, which could reduce risk of delay but may also impact resource planning and stakeholder expectations.

Finally, more conservative estimations made by the GAN do not necessarily result in more accurate predictions, but they offer greater security in terms of scheduling, cost control, and stakeholder confidence.

5. CONCLUSION

The advances in AI technologies, such as machine learning and predictive analytics, is reshaping project management by enhancing the precision of outcome forecasting. These advanced tools enable early detection of potential risks, including schedule delays, budget overruns, and resource limitations, thereby supporting timely and informed decision-making.

This paper deals with a specific area of the application of AI techniques in project estimations and predictive analytics, and more specifically with the data scarcity challenge. The focus is on applying Generative Adversarial Networks for generating project task estimates for a new project with a certain level of complexity. The scope of the new project differed from that of the historical projects used as reference. Nevertheless, this historical data served as the training foundation for the GAN model, enabling it to generate realistic and contextually relevant project outputs. Four variations of GANs were considered as part of this experiment, each with different training duration, batch size, regularization techniques, and loss functions. For the evaluation of model performance, two accuracy metrics were used MAE and Fréchet Distance. The obtained results are compared with traditional estimation approach to assess accuracy, variance, and overall project planning efficiency. GAN-based model V3 estimated a total project duration of 149.52 days, compared to 123.31 days using traditional methods, indicating a 21% increase. This may suggest that the synthetic model accounted for potential complexities often overlooked, offering a more cautious yet potentially more realistic outlook that may help mitigate delivery risks.

This experiment demonstrated the potential of GANs to generate realistic project estimates based on historical data, even when applied to a project with a different scope. By comparing synthetic and traditional estimates, it was observed how AI-based models can reveal hidden complexities and provide more conservative planning baselines. As a next step, the approach could be extended to (1) generate additional dimensions such as resource allocations, and dependencies, and (2) validated across a broader dataset. Integrating these models into project management workflows could support more informed decision-making. Ultimately, these results may lay the foundation for implementing a Jira plugin that enhances proactive risk management.

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